

Real and synthetic scenarios generated for the development, training, virtual testing and validation of CCAM systems

SYNERGIES

Project Website

Document Type	Deliverable
Document Number	D10.2
Primary Author(s)	Michael Karner Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH
Document Version / Status	1.0 Final
Distribution Level	PU (public)

Project Acronym	SYNERGIES
Project Website	www.synergies-ccam.eu
Project Coordinator	IDIADA AUTOMOTIVE TECHNOLOGY SA
Grant Agreement Number	101146542
Date of latest version of Annex I against which the assessment will be made	2024-05-27

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

CONTRIBUTORS

Name	Organization	Name	Organization
Michael Karner	VIF		
Elisabeth Ulbel	VIF		

FORMAL REVIEWERS

Name	Organization	Date
Marc Perez	IDIADA	2024-10-14
Jordi Pont	IDIADA	2024-10-24

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Revision	Date	Author Organization	Description
0.1	2024-09-23	Michael Karner VIF	Created initial structure of the deliverable.
0.2	2024-10-04	Michael Karner VIF	Added content, refined structure.
0.3	2024-10-15	Michael Karner VIF	Update after review.
1.0	2024-10-16	Michael Karner VIF	Updated screenshots based on latest website updates.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
2	SYNERGIES WEBSITE	7
2.1	Introduction and intended audience	7
2.2	Contribution to objectives	8
2.3	Key performance indicators (KPIs)	9
2.4	Website structure	11
3	CONCLUSIONS	16
4	REFERENCES	17
A.	ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS	18

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 SYNERGIES Website (excerpt)	7
Figure 2 The Project	11
Figure 3 Partners (excerpt)	12
Figure 4 Results	13
Figure 5 News.....	14
Figure 6 Contact.....	15

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 KPIs for the SYNERGIES website.....10

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 10.2 (D10.2) offers an overview of the SYNERGIES project's website, its main features, its goals and the pages it consists of.

D10.2 complements deliverable 10.1 [1], which contains SYNERGIES's communication and dissemination strategy and plan. There, target audiences, dissemination and communication activities and channels that will be used throughout the project are proposed.

VIRTUAL VEHICLE as WP10 leader coordinated the design and the content of the website, in alignment with the SYNERGIES coordinator IDIADA.

Keywords: Website, communication, dissemination, cooperation

2 SYNERGIES WEBSITE

2.1 Introduction and intended audience

The **project website** (<https://www.synergies-ccam.eu/>) has come online in October 2024.

It provides an easy-to-read introduction to the project, its objectives, partners and means of contact. It also informs about current (project-related) news and activities and of course acts as repository for (public) deliverables.

Figure 1 SYNERGIES Website (excerpt)

All partners in the project are encouraged to use their own company or institute websites to link and promote the SYNERGIES project. Ideally, links to SYNERGIES project website will be made from most of the partner websites.

An easy to find project website is essential to make the project known, and to disseminate results.

Our intended audience includes

- Potential customers for SYNERGIES's exploitable foreground
- Experts in industry and academia interested in using or referring to SYNERGIES results
- Research and education organisation interested in the body of knowledge resulting from SYNERGIES
- General public interested in state of the art and ongoing research of development, training, virtual testing, and validation of connected, cooperative, and automated mobility (CCAM) systems
- Governmental organisations, standards organisations, non-governmental organisations (NGO) etc. looking for related expertise

To fulfil its goal, the SYNERGIES website was designed and is continuously maintained with search-engine optimization (SEO) in mind.

2.2 Contribution to objectives

The SYNERGIES website contributes to the following SYNERGIES objectives:

- Objective 1: Building the project awareness beyond the scope of the consortium
- Objective 2: Effective dissemination of project results via multiple channels.
- Objective 3: Communicating the project results and achievements to external parties

2.3 Key performance indicators (KPIs)

Using the following three search engines in a private session (non-personalized) in Firefox we will periodically check and report on rankings for typical search strings relating to SYNERGIES.

1. <https://www.google.com/>
2. <https://www.qwant.com/>
3. <http://www.baidu.com>

Table 1 contains an overview on the communication & dissemination KPIs.

Channel	Purpose	Target Groups	Metrics	Target
Website	Public information and all public deliverables, online destination for target audiences (knowledge hub)	Policy makers/authorities, general public, end-users, standardization bodies, automotive industry, research community	Ranking on Google search term <i>CCAM SYNERGIES project</i>	Ranked 1 st
Website	Public information and all public deliverables, online destination for target audiences (knowledge hub)	Policy makers/authorities, general public, end-users, standardization bodies, automotive industry, research community	Ranking on Qwant search term <i>CCAM SYNERGIES project</i>	Ranked 1 st
Website	Public information and all public deliverables, online destination for target audiences (knowledge hub)	Policy makers/authorities, general public, end-users, standardization bodies, automotive industry, research community	Ranking on Baidu search term <i>CCAM SYNERGIES project</i>	Ranked 1 st
Website	Public information and all public deliverables, online destination for target audiences (knowledge hub)	Policy makers/authorities, general public, end-users, standardization bodies, automotive industry, research community	Ranking on Google search term <i>Scenarios for development, training, virtual testing and validation of CCAM systems</i>	Ranked 1 st

Channel	Purpose	Target Groups	Metrics	Target
Website	Public information and all public deliverables, online destination for target audiences (knowledge hub)	Policy makers/authorities, general public, end-users, standardization bodies, automotive industry, research community	Ranking on Qwant search term <i>Scenarios for development, training, virtual testing and validation of CCAM systems</i>	Ranked 1 st
Website	Public information and all public deliverables, online destination for target audiences (knowledge hub)	Policy makers/authorities, general public, end-users, standardization bodies, automotive industry, research community	Ranking on Baidu search term <i>Scenarios for development, training, virtual testing and validation of CCAM systems</i>	Ranked 1 st
Website	Public information and all public deliverables, online destination for target audiences (knowledge hub)	Policy makers/authorities, general public, end-users, standardization bodies, automotive industry, research community	Ranking on Google search term <i>CCAM scenario database</i>	Ranked top ten
Website	Public information and all public deliverables, online destination for target audiences (knowledge hub)	Policy makers/authorities, general public, end-users, standardization bodies, automotive industry, research community	Ranking on Qwant search term <i>CCAM scenario database</i>	Ranked top ten
Website	Public information and all public deliverables, online destination for target audiences (knowledge hub)	Policy makers/authorities, general public, end-users, standardization bodies, automotive industry, research community	Ranking on Baidu search term <i>CCAM scenario database</i>	Ranked top ten
Website	Public information and all public deliverables, online destination for target audiences (knowledge hub)	Policy makers/authorities, general public, end-users, standardization bodies, automotive industry, research community	#unique visitors #news postings	≥1000 views/year, ≥12 news/year

Table 1 KPIs for the SYNERGIES website

2.4 Website structure

The SYNERGIES website contains the following pages:

- [HOME](#) → Main page with important facts and key information about the project like vision and mission, and latest news. Also includes a link to social media and the required disclaimer (see Figure 1).
- [THE PROJECT](#) → Detailed information about the project including challenges and objectives.
- [PARTNERS](#) → List of consortium partners with short description and official websites.
- [RESULTS](#) → Public SYNERGIES results including information material, public deliverables, media materials, and publications.
- [NEWS](#) → Latest news from the SYNERGIES project.
- [CONTACT](#) → Contact form.

Screenshots of the pages are included below.

Figure 2 The Project

Partners

 IDIADA AUTOMOTIVE TECHNOLOGY SA (IDI)	 BAYERISCHE MOTOREN WERKE AKTIENGESELLSCHAFT (BMW)	 STELLANTIS AUTO SAS (PSA)	 RENAULT SAS (REN)

Figure 3 Partners (excerpt)

Results

- Information Material
- Public Deliverables
- Media
- Publications

Contact Project coordinator Jordi Pont Project Communication Email: synergies@v2c2.at Imprint & Terms of Use	Disclaimer SYNERGIES has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101146542. This website reflects only the author's view and neither the European Commission nor CINEA is responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.	Social Funded by the European Union	
---	---	--	--

Figure 4 Results

News

SYNERGIES

SYNERGIES Kick-Off

Sep 10, 2024

We are excited to share that SYNERGIES has successfully achieved its first project milestone! In June, the project partners gathered in Spain at the headquarters of our coordinator, IDIADA Automotive Technology SA, to discuss the next steps during the official project...

Figure 5 News

**Questions or suggestions?
Contact us via the form below!**

**Feel free to reach out to us if you have any
questions or would like to cooperate!**

Figure 6 Contact

3 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable explains the structure and characteristics of the SYNERGIES website, together with a list of KPIs. The website contains the main information and updates about the project, and, together with social media, is the main tool to communicate and disseminate the SYNERGIES achievements externally. The website will be regularly maintained and updated.

4 REFERENCES

- [1] SYNERGIES Deliverable D10.1: Dissemination and Communication Plan, September 2024.

A. ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS

Term	Definition
CCAM	Connected, Cooperative, and Automated Mobility
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure, and Environment Executive Agency
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
SYNERGIES	Real and Synthetic Scenarios Generated for the Development, Training, Virtual Testing and Validation of CCAM Systems
WP	Work Package